

Synthesis of Piperovatine

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The reaction of phosphonate of ethyl crotonate with *p*-methoxyphenyl acetaldehyde (V) yields ethyl 6(*p*-methoxyphenyl)-hexa *trans*-2, *trans*-4 dienoate (VI). This unsaturated ester (VI) on hydrolysis and treatment with thionyl chloride followed by the reaction of isobutyl amine gives piperovatine. The aldehyde (V) was obtained from the corresponding acid (II), through its chloride (III), anilide (IV), followed by LiAlH_4 reduction of the anilide.

DUNSTAN and Garnett¹ in 1895 isolated piperovatine from the leaves of shrub *ottonia vahlilii* (syn. *piper Ovatum*). The compound was shown to have marked physiological properties like that of temporary nerve depressant, a heart poison, a local anesthetic and a powerful sialagogue when applied to the tongue. Recently Price and Pinder² isolated the compound from the same plant and established its structure (I) through spectral data, chemical degradation and synthesis.

In the present communication we report a new synthesis of the title compound. The modified Wittig reaction of γ -phosphonate of ethyl crotonate with *p*-methoxyphenyl acetaldehyde is a key step for the projected synthesis. Recent studies show that Wittig reaction^{3,4,5} of ylids enjoying resonance stabilization with aldehydes tend to be stereospecific and yield a great preponderance of *trans* olefins. On the basis of these observations and comparison of spectral data of *N*-Isobutyl 6(*p*-methoxyphenyl) hexa-*trans*-2, *trans*-4, dienoic acid amide (Natural piperovatine) and our synthetic product it has been concluded that our synthetic product has the same stereochemistry for the two side chain double bonds conjugated with the amide carbonyl group.

p-Methoxyphenyl acetic acid (II) was prepared from *p*-methoxy acetophenone⁶. The corresponding acid chloride(III) was prepared by treatment of acid(II) with thionyl chloride which was further reacted with methyl aniline in pyridine solution to get *p*-methoxyphenyl *N*-methyl acetanilide (IV) in 86% yield. The anilide (IV) was reduced with LiAlH_4 by the procedure of Nigam and Weedon⁷ to furnish *p*-methoxyphenyl acetaldehyde

(V). The aldehyde (V) was characterised through its IR absorption bands at 1730 and 2730 cm^{-1} .

Our attempt to prepare the aldehyde (V) from *p*-methoxyphenyl acetic acid(II) by esterification, reduction with LiAlH_4 and oxidation of the alcohol by pyridine chromic oxide always furnished a mixture of the products. The separation of the mixture was not attempted and the above alternate route of reduction of anilide was followed to prepare the required aldehyde(V).

p-Methoxyphenyl acetaldehyde (V) was submitted to the modified Wittig reaction with γ -phosphonate of ethyl crotonate in the presence of NaH using diglyme as solvent⁸. γ -Phosphonate of ethyl crotonate was prepared from triethyl phosphite and γ -bromo ethyl crotonate by Michaelis Arbusov reaction. This resulted in the formation of ethyl 6(*p*-methoxyphenyl) hexa-*trans*-2, *trans*-4 dienoate (VI) in 72% yield. IR showed

characteristic absorption bands at 1715 (conj. ester) and 995 (*trans* double bonds) cm^{-1} . The conjugated ester(VI) was hydrolysed with 30% Hydrochloric acid to afford the corresponding acid(VII) m.p. 115° (lit.² m.p. 115°). The acid was treated with thionyl chloride at room

temperature to furnish the acid chloride (VIII), which on further reaction with isobutylamine provided N-isobutyl 6(*p*-methoxyphenyl) hexa-*trans*-2, *trans*-4-dienoic acid amide in crude form (piperovatine). It was crystallized from critical volume of ether and had m.p. 121° (lit.² m.p. 121°). The structure (I) was characterized through IR, UV and NMR; $\nu_{\max}^{\text{nujol}}$ 3400, 1670, 1650, 1625, 995 cm^{-1} (consistent) with

($\epsilon = 25000$); NMR (δ , PPM) 6.9 (4H, arom.; m), 5.6-6.4 (4H, olef., complex m), 3.71 (3H, OCH₃, S), 3.35 (2H, Bnzy., d), 3.10 (2H, methylene of isobutyl, t), 1.2 (1H tert. H, m), 0.88 (6H, methyl, d).

IR, UV and NMR spectral data of our synthesised product are in good agreement with the spectral data reported for natural and synthesised pipervatine².

Experimental

The melting and boiling points are uncorrected. IR spectra were recorded on Perkin-Elmer infracord with sodium chloride optics using a thin liquid film and NMR spectra of solutions in carbon tetrachloride using tetramethylsilane as an internal standard at 60 Mc/Sc.

P-Methoxyphenyl *N*-methyl acetanilide (IV): To a solution of *p*-methoxyphenyl acetic acid (II, 10g) in dry benzene (50 ml.) was slowly added thionyl chloride (7.8 g). The contents were heated under reflux until the evolution of HCl gas had ceased. Un-reacted thionyl chloride and benzene were removed under partial vacuum and the residue on distillation b.p. 120-125/8-10 mm, furnished the acid chloride (III) 8.5 g, 77%.

A solution of methyl aniline (6 g) in equal volume of pyridine was slowly added to the cooled and stirred acid chloride (III, 8.5 g) taken in dry benzene (75 ml.). After the addition of methylaniline the mixture was further stirred at 20° for 1/2 hr. and it was then decomposed with water and extracted with benzene. The benzene extract was thoroughly washed with 2*N* HCl, water and then dried. The solvent was removed and the residue on distillation b.p. 190-95/8-10 mm furnished IV, (10.2 g, 86%). IR absorption showed bands at 1650, 1620, 1600, 1500, 1375, 1300, 1250, 1180, 1120, 1075, 1035, 920, 860, 825, 775, 745 and 700 cm^{-1} .

P-Methoxyphenyl acetaldehyde (V): A solution of LiAlH₄ (460 mg.) in dry ether (80 ml) was added slowly to a cooled and well stirred solution of methyl anilide (IV) (10 g) in ether (25 ml.). After the mixture had been stirred at 0° for 2 hrs.; a small volume of ethyl acetate was added to decompose the excess of hydride, followed by 2*N* HCl and water. The Organic layer was separated and the aqueous layer was extracted with ether (3 × 50 ml.). The combined ethereal extract was washed with water (2 × 10 ml.) and then dried, solvent removed and the residue distilled at b.p. 135-40/8-10 mm to afford V, (2.6 g., 45%). IR absorption showed bands at 2850, 2730, 1725, 1625, 1600, 1510, 1450, 1315, 1265, 1185, 1115, 1040, 935, 820, 780, 760 and 695 cm^{-1} .

Ethyl 6(p-methoxyphenyl) hexa-trans-2, trans-4 dienoate (VI): Sodium hydride (0.940 g, 50%) was washed with *n*-hexane and taken in diglyme (30 ml.). Ethyl- γ -diethyl phosphono crotonate (5.0 g) was added dropwise below 20° with stirring. The solution was stirred until the gas evolution has ceased. It was cooled to 0° and the aldehyde (V, 2.5 g) added dropwise with constant stirring. After the addition of the aldehyde the solution was stirred for another 2 hr and then warmed at 60° for 1/2 hr. It was then decomposed with cold water extracted with ether and the combined ethereal extract washed with water and dried. After the removal of the solvent, the residue was distilled b.p. 170°-75°/8-10 mm., to give VI, (2.90 g, 72%). IR absorption spectrum showed bands at 1715, 1610, 1510, 1460, 1450, 1300, 1250, 1180, 1110, 1035, 995, 830, 760 and 680 cm^{-1} .

(Found C, 73.02, H, 7.235; C₁₅H₁₈O₃ requires C 73.170, H, 7.317%)

6(p-Methoxyphenyl) hexa-trans-2, trans-4 dienoic acid (VII): The ester (VI, 2.8 g) was hydrolysed with 30% hydrochloric acid according to the method reported². The acid after crystallisation from petroleum ether melted at 114°-115°.

(Found C, 71.350; H, 6.385; C₁₃H₁₄O₃ requires C, 71.561; H, 6.422).

N-Isobutyl - 6(*p*-methoxyphenyl) hexa-*trans*-2, *trans*-4 dienoic acid amide (I): Acid (VII, 1.00 g) was taken in dry benzene (25 ml.), contents were warmed at 50° for 1/2 hr. Unreacted thionyl chloride and benzene were removed under reduced pressure and the residue furnished the crude acid chloride (VIII, 0.75 g, 75%).

The acid chloride (VIII) in crude form was taken in dry ether, cooled and treated with isobutylamine (2.2 g). After decomposition and solvent evaporation solid residue was obtained, get formation was observed with ether as observed by others², however it was possible to crystallize the compound (I) using critical volume of ether m.p. 120°-121°. Tlc gave single spot. IR, UV and NMR are reported in the discussion portion. (Found N, 5.150, C₁₇H₂₁NO₂ required N, 5.166).

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